

MEDICAL SERVICES ON DIGITAL ECONOMY AND LAW

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Internet technologies are greatly helping the development of the healthcare industry. In particular, IT systems have become vital in the provision of modern health services.

In addition, the constant growth of the world's population, various diseases, and the consequences of the pandemic are causing the need for medical services to increase even more. According to the calculations of the World Health Organization, the world population reached 7 billion in 2011, and in 2021 this figure will be almost 7.9 billion. The world population is expected to grow to 8.5 billion in 2030, 9.7 billion in 2050, and 10.9 billion in 2100¹.

Concepts such as digitization, use of digital technologies, use of artificial intelligence and nanotechnology are taking place in our vocabulary in every field. Of course, the pace of innovation and technological processes is felt more in the areas that directly serve people or make their lives easier. This can be taken as an example of the field of medical services.

This dramatic increase is largely due to an increase in the number of people surviving to reproductive age, accompanied by large changes in fertility rates, urbanization and accelerated migration. These trends will have major implications for future generations.

Therefore, it is natural that the need for medical services is greater than ever. In particular, the spread of the 2019 Covid-19 disease in the last 2019 and it will reach the level of a global pandemic by 2020, unlike traditional methods of providing medical services, online platforms, active software on the Internet the process of implementation on the basis of supplies and artificial intelligence has accelerated.

The digital economy has characteristics that are important for the operation of each sector. The most important issue is economic relations related to the development of IT and artificial intelligence. Digital technologies are penetrating various segments of the economy, including banking, retail, energy, transportation, education, mass media, healthcare, and information and communication.

It should be noted that the diversity of today's needs and offers has strengthened the desire of entrepreneurs to work in a new way and even forced them to do so. There are a number of reasons for this.

First, daily usage of the Internet in the service market, a new approach and enthusiasm for work has increased. As a result, the creation of electronic software, the production of databases increased, and the use of each field employee based on his ability and needs increased.

Second, a number of offline services are now available on the Internet and have proven to be convenient for people.

Thirdly, rendering of online services leads to excessive time consumption and cost savings.

Fourth, due to the rise of remote services, earning opportunities have increased and age limits have become less important in online careers.

¹ <https://www.un.org/en/observances/world-population-day>

Fifth, unnecessary interference by state authorities and excessive bureaucratic obstacles have been reduced to a minimum.

Online medical consultation is more important in modern times, especially since COVID-19 has made it more relevant than ever. Further research is needed to validate this technique in plastic surgery. There is a clear need to standardize medical consultation procedures, channels, encryption and data storage, while maintaining quality of care and social distancing.

In the 21st century, some doctors and surgeons are reinventing medicine. Working with labs, scientists are testing new technologies, from software to robotics, that could revolutionize the medical environment, providing better outcomes, lower costs, greater access, and greater convenience.

According to the definition of Russian scientists, "Digital medicine is a system of scientific knowledge and practical activities for diagnosis, treatment and prevention of disease, and digital health care that collects, preserves and develops the system of scientific knowledge in the field of medicine to preserve and strengthen human health and work ability, prolong life, as well as on the basis of the platform to claim and provide services to those suffering from physical and mental diseases based on information and communication technologies².

According to Joseph C. Kvedar, Alexander Fogel, Eric Elenko, and Daphne Zohar, digital medicine is considered the most dynamic new type of interdisciplinary practice in terms of theory, knowledge, technology, methodology, and innovation³. Digital medicine implements the latest paradigms and methods, and recently uses IT products, such as imaging techniques and robotic surgery.

Today, online medical services are being implemented on the basis of telemedicine. For this reason, when determining online medical services, it is advisable to first study the companies that perform this activity and the services they offer.

According to information provided by GovHealth online magazine⁴, Teladoc, MEMD, ICliniq, Amwell, MDlive, Doctor on Demand, Virtuwel and the services they provide are listed. Taking ICliniq as an example, like other telemedicine providers, iCliniq offers a wide range of services for patients and they can book an appointment online in advance. Patients can also provide doctors with their medical history, request a phone interview or video call.

The study showed that in many foreign countries (the USA, Germany, Singapore, Norway, Russia⁵, etc.), the legal regulation of the field of telemedicine is provided for in regulatory legal documents.

In particular, in the USA, there are separate laws at both the federal and state levels that clearly define the concept of telemedicine, the scope of entities, their rights and obligations, as well as regulating issues of licensing, liability and personal data protection.

² Карпов О. Э., Субботин С. А., Шишканов Д. В., Замятин М. Н. Цифровое здравоохранение. Необходимость и предпосылки <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tsifrovoe-zdravoohranenie-neobhodimost-i-predposylki/viewer>

³ Kvedar, J. C., Fogel, A. L., Elenko, E., & Zohar, D. (2016). Digital medicine's march on chronic disease. *Nature Biotechnology*, 34(3), 239–246. doi:10.1038/nbt.3495

⁴ <https://www.govhealthit.com/telemedicine-companies>

⁵ Сазонова М. Доктор онлайн: правовые аспекты телемедицины в России // <https://www.garant.ru/article/1405237/>

As Internet use and technology become increasingly intertwined in everyday life, the use of telemedicine is increasing. According to the American Hospital Association⁶ (AHA), more than 50% of hospital systems have used some form of telemedicine. For this reason, the legal basis of the needs in this direction has been created. But it is interesting that states in the USA are regulated based on their territorial laws.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of online medical services is one of the areas that is expected to become popular not only today, but also in the near future. During the global pandemic, the population of the whole world has become a clear witness of this by using medical services as well as using various remote services. The rapid development of the digitization process was the impetus for this. The use of the mechanism of practical operation of online medical services requires a number of changes and additions to the legislation, as well as re-examination of issues related to the identification of a person in the use of services.

Secondly, it is necessary to guarantee the patient's rights even when using any form of medical services. This process needs to be clarified with a certain boundary between receiving a consultation from a specialist at a distance and being present in front of the specialist, because the human factor, not being able to tell the details requested by the doctor or hiding them as a personal secret can put a person's life at risk.

Thirdly, it is necessary to form a patient database and provide an electronic system. It is necessary to provide a sufficient base for this, especially for state medical institutions.

Fourthly, we believe that it is appropriate to indicate the use of electronic document circulation, means of personal identification when concluding contracts, and the consequences of non-fulfillment of obligations in the Civil and Health Codes, which are expected to be adopted.

The use of advanced technologies in the provision of medical services has become not only today's tool, but also a means of making everyone's burden light and distances closer. In this process, it is necessary to apply legal regulatory mechanisms, based on them, to revise the relations that are moving from the usual form to the electronic form. When creating the legislative base, it is necessary to take into account scientific and theoretical conclusions, to apply general and private principles of law.

In accordance with the purpose of mutual analysis of the legal consequences of providing services in a simple way and determining the measures of responsibility in relation to the legal consequences of providing online medical services and its implementation. Equality and consideration of the real situation in determining the measures of responsibility increases the confidence of the users of the service that there is a legal guarantee.

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⁶ Trendwatch: The promise of telehealth for hospitals, health systems, and their communities. Washington, DC: American Hospital Association; 2015. Available at: www.aha.org/research/reports/tw/15jan-tw-telehealth.pdf. Last accessed 12 Mar 2020.

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